

A MULTIFACETED APP FOR SUPPORTING COMMUNICATION IN GREEK: THE CASE OF “SPEAK ON THE SPOT”

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Abstract

Digital Technologies impose new challenges to language learning in the 21st century which affect the relationship among language learning, technology and pedagogy. Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) offers new possibilities to learners and makes foreign language learning more accessible. Owners of a smartphone have at their disposal new means to practice a foreign language in various locations and situations. The aim of this paper is to describe “Speak on the Spot” (<http://www.xanthi.ilsp.gr/test/speakonthespot/>), a multifaceted app for iOS and Android smartphones. For the design of the app and the development of the linguistic material, we have considered the results of research on existing apps for learning Greek as a foreign language and of questionnaires used to elicit the opinion of possible users so as to define the needs and expectations of our target group from an app of this kind. All the principles and restrictions of MALL have also been taken into consideration.

“Speak on the Spot” is addressed to all foreigners who visit Greece for business or pleasure and wish to communicate with the locals; they can be either absolute beginners or have some prior knowledge of Greek. English and Chinese have been used as supportive languages. The app is suitable for self-learning as well as for practicing the language in authentic communicative situations in hotels or while wandering around a Greek city. The language content consists of a brief introduction on the Greek language (alphabet, letter combinations, stress), basic and thematic vocabulary, expressions and short dialogues that are useful for tourists. Audio recording, translation, illustration, phonetic transcription, a voice recording tool and a search tool have been added as means that facilitate the learning procedure. The material is divided in short but independent segments to allow users to spend no more than 10-15 minutes using the app.

What differentiates “Speak on the Spot” from other existing apps is the possibility of customizing it to the needs and services of various partners involved in the tourist sector. Hotels, sight-seeing companies, airports, airlines and other transport companies, malls and educational institutions can upgrade and advertise the services they provide to enhance the experience of their guests. The paper describes the technical requirements of two levels of customization: customization with few adaptations and customisation with major modifications. In the first case, the app is interspersed with photographic and other promotional material of the company/institution to highlight the services provided. In the second case, customization involves adaptation of the content and other multimedia material to reflect the actual hotel, shopping mall etc. Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) beacons and/or GPS can be used for context-aware learning environments; they can be placed inside a hotel or a city shop and push notifications on users’ mobile devices with the corresponding expressions that they need to use in the specific location.

Keywords: mobile app, learning Greek, customization of an app, BLE beacons.

1 INTRODUCTION

At the outset of the 21st century, the relationship among language learning, technology and pedagogy needs to be redefined. New educational approaches are essential to make language learning accessible to everyone; technology and, more particularly, Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) can offer new possibilities in language learning [1]. In fact, smartphones could be transformed into useful tools for foreign language learning offering users motivation and supportive learning environments. Mobile foreign language learning can be enhanced when users are engaged in authentic communicative situations, i.e., by performing location dependent and location aware tasks in the real world that speaks the target language. Location independent learning activities, on the other hand, provide the flexibility of learning anytime, anywhere [2]. High quality language material, new practice opportunities, audio and video are also crucial elements of MALL; all these allow knowledge to be constructed in various contexts and users acquire new skills by getting involved in different communicative activities.

The purpose of this paper is to describe “Speak on the Spot”, a multifaceted app addressed to all foreigners visiting Greece. The design of the app has been based upon market research and evaluation

of all existing apps for learning Greek as foreign language, a needs analysis of the target group using questionnaires, as well as on the principles and restrictions imposed by MALL [3]. The generic app "Speak on the Spot" can be downloaded by users from Google Play or Appstore but can also be adapted to the needs and services of various tourist companies. The procedure of customization involves adaptation of the multimedia material, customization of content and possibility of automatic access to the communicative material using GPS, beacons, and other technologies.

2 DESIGN METHODOLOGY

In order to design an application suitable for foreigners and especially for tourists visiting Greece, we have initially taken into consideration the results of research in the field of MALL for Greek as a foreign language (see [4] for a detailed overview of this research). Some of the existing apps contain very interesting features, like rich and carefully organized language material, high quality recordings or advanced technology tools. Still, improvements can be made concerning the quality and quantity of the content, the tools provided and the possibilities of real time use that an app can offer.

Before deciding on the content and the main features of our app, we conducted research to investigate the needs of our target group. For this reason, we prepared and distributed a questionnaire in Greek (but also in English, for the very beginners) to be completed by foreigners living in Greece who have experienced the need to communicate in Greek with the locals.

We have collected 37 questionnaires from which we gathered interesting feedback on the needs and expectations of our target group. Initially, 9 out of 10 had access to the internet and, therefore, they have the possibility to download mobile apps. Concerning the language material: 41% responded that they need access to a dictionary, 30% need useful phrases in short dialogues, 17% need grammar and 12% long dialogues.

As far as a supportive language is concerned, 51% expressed a high need for material translated in their mother tongue, 19% expressed moderate need and 11% no need for a supportive language at all. 91% of the respondents prefer English to be the supportive language and only 9% French.

Audio recordings by native speakers of Greek is a feature that 8 out of 10 respondents find very helpful. Concerning the International Phonetic Alphabet, only 41% are sure that they need it and another 40% may find it useful. Illustration is very helpful for 6 out of 10 respondents and rather helpful for another 24%.

Taking into consideration that Greek is a language with a complex morphological system, we have incorporated in the questionnaire a question on the need to include grammar teaching in an app. All respondents find it helpful to have access to short grammar material; more particularly, 35% need verb declension, 25% noun and adjective declension, 21% instruction on the Greek alphabet and 19% on stress. As far as exercises in concerned, 43% prefer multiple choice questions, 36% filling in blanks and 21% voice recording exercises. On the questions on the use of a search tool, 81% of the respondents think that it is useful to have a tool that permits search in both Greek and the users' mother tongue.

Half of the respondents (51%) are ready to download an app for learning Greek on their phone, 43% may do that and only 6% won't do it. When exploring what guides their decision to download an app, 46% replied that they download an app only if this is free, another 28% considers the opinion of those who have already used the app and, finally, the remaining 26% takes into consideration the size of the app.

3 DEVELOPING A NEW MULTIFACETED APP FOR SUPPORTING COMMUNICATION IN GREEK

"Speak on the Spot" is a mobile app for iOS and Android smartphones, with English or Chinese as supportive language; it is addressed to all foreigners who visit Greece for business or pleasure and wish to communicate with the locals. Besides the research described above, we have also taken into consideration the principles and restrictions imposed by MALL [3] as well as the fact that although we spend a lot of time during the day with a mobile phone in our hands, the time we spend on a single application is ultimately limited. Based on the above, the language material has been divided in short but independent segments to allow users to organize their study time; for instance, a letter of the alphabet can be studied in two minutes, an expression may need five and a short dialogue can take no more than ten minutes. Eventually, the suggested study time does not exceed 10-15 minutes.

Irrespective of the level of proficiency of users, translation is considered an essential element for self-learning, therefore, we used English and Chinese as supportive languages. A search tool from English

or Chinese and from Greek provides further assistance during navigation through the material. Despite the fact that the respondents of our questionnaires claimed that grammar teaching is helpful, we decided to adopt a communicative approach without formal teaching of grammatical phenomena; beginners can profit from the material on the Greek alphabet, letter combinations and stress.

3.1 “Speak [Greek] on the Spot”: an ideal assistant for all foreigners

"Speak on the Spot" is suitable for self-learning as well as for practicing the language in authentic communicative situations in hotels or while wandering around a Greek city. The generic app contains the following five (5) units with multimedia material produced by experienced linguistics to suit the needs of both absolute beginners and users with some prior knowledge of the language:

- Let's read Greek (Ας διαβάσουμε Ελληνικά)
- The basics (Τα βασικά)
- Thematic Vocabulary (Θεματικό Λεξιλόγιο)
- Let's speak Greek in the hotel (Ας μιλήσουμε Ελληνικά στο ξενοδοχείο)
- Let's speak Greek around the city (Ας μιλήσουμε Ελληνικά στην πόλη)

3.1.1 *Let's read Greek*

This unit is addressed mainly to beginners with no previous knowledge of the language. Users get acquainted with the Greek alphabet and letter combinations, as well as the use of stress. When selecting to study e.g., a letter (Fig. 1), they can listen to its pronunciation and read the phonetic transcription. Moreover, they can read an example of a word in English or Chinese containing the sound of the letter, as well as a Greek word containing this letter, with phonetic transcription, translation and illustration.

Figure 1: The Greek alphabet - The letter Γ, γ.

Advanced learners of Greek profit from this unit to get acquainted with the symbols of phonetic transcription. Finally, the exercises of this unit give users of all levels the chance to practice their speaking skills by recording their voice and comparing it to that of native speakers.

3.1.2 *The Basics*

In this unit, users can find a list of 65 words or expressions of everyday use (in English or Chinese). By choosing a word, they can read it in Greek, listen to the audio recording as many times as they wish and consult the phonetic transcription.

3.1.3 Thematic Vocabulary

The unit contains 170 illustrated words (in English or Chinese) divided in 13 thematic areas (numbers, seasons, days, time, items of personal hygiene, clothes, souvenirs, food, sweets/drinks/refreshments, fruits & vegetables, months, means of transport, travel items). By choosing a word, they can read it in Greek, listen to the audio recording as many times as they wish and consult the phonetic transcription.

3.1.4 Let's speak Greek in the hotel.

This unit consists of 83 short, illustrated dialogues that take place around hotel premises. It is mainly addressed to foreigners with basic knowledge of Greek. They can choose the material from a list of locations inside and outside a hotel (at the reception, in the room, at the swimming pool etc.) and a sub-list of communicative situations (getting the key, asking the cleaner, ordering breakfast etc.).

When selecting a dialogue (Fig. 2), users have the following options:

- To read the dialogue in Greek and listen to the audio recording by native speakers as many times as they wish,
- To consult the phonetic transcription that will help them in their reading,
- To read the translation in English or Chinese that will help them to understand the meaning,
- To choose a role and record their voice when performing the dialogic part. Then, they can listen to the dialogue with their own participation in it.

Figure 2: At the hotel reception – Arriving at the hotel.

3.1.5 Let's speak Greek around the city.

This unit contains 245 illustrated useful phrases addressed to foreigners who want to practice Greek while walking around the city. They can first select from the available listed places the one they find themselves in, then select the type of communicative situation they want to participate in and, finally, the expression they need. Users have the possibility to read it, listen to the recording as many times as they need and study the phonetic transcription (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Around the city - In the bus.

The high-quality language material of the generic app can be used in two ways:

- In a self-learning context (at home, at work, on the plane etc.) And at their own pace
- In real time when wandering in the hotel premises or in the city shops. The user-friendly interface and the search tool facilitate access to the material. Users, in this case, can communicate 'on the spot' with the locals.

3.2 Towards customizing “Speak on the Spot”

The generic version of “Speak on the Spot” has been developed with English or Chinese as supportive languages. Other supportive languages can be added to match the needs of foreigners of different nationalities. What differentiated this app from others is the possibility of customizing it to the needs and services of various partners involved in the tourist sector, thus allowing them to upgrade their services and enhance the experience of their clients. In fact, it can work as an additional advertising channel; when tourists get back home, they can share the content of the app with their friends [5].

The customization process can be simple (with few modifications) or more complex (with major modification).

3.2.1 Customization with few modifications

Tourist companies and educational institutions can get their own "Speak on the Spot" customized to the needs of their clients or students with few adaptations. The end product will highlight the services of the company/institution and incorporate the corresponding photographic and other promotional material. This may constitute a very important differential competitive advantage in the services sector. More particularly:

- Hotels and cruise ships can have a customized version of the app that reflects the actual services and premises; for instance, if the hotel has no spa or swimming pool, the corresponding material should be omitted. Pictures from the actual hotel will be added (e.g., the reception area, the hotel room etc.). Users can download the app when making their reservation or checking in and familiarize themselves with the facilities and premises.

- Airlines and other transport companies can offer "Speak on the Spot" to their passengers for self-learning on board, thus, allowing them to enjoy their free time and profit from advertising their offers through the app.
- Sight-seeing companies and travel agencies can offer their clients an e-assistant for their communication in Greek when visiting the city stores or while taking a tour of the city's attractions. Offers and other promotional material can be made available through the app.
- Educational institutions and private schools can offer their students "Speak on the Spot" as a communicative assistant when using Greek in real time situations. Students can then discuss difficulties and exchange their experiences in the classroom.
- Shopping malls and airports can customize "Speak on the Spot" and advertise their offers through the app. Users will profit from the offers and use the app in their communication with the staff.

3.2.2 Customization with major modifications

The procedure of customizing "Speak on the Spot" involves additional adaptations of the multimedia content and incorporation of technological means that allow real time access to the communicative material.

✦ Customization of the content

The content (text and accompanying multimedia material) of the generic app can be adapted in various ways or new content can be added, if necessary. For example, hotels and cruise ships can add dialogues customized to the specific features and services of their premises. Answers to questions like "What is the Wi-Fi password?", "Where is the toilet?" or "Where is the breakfast area?", "Do you have a SPA room?", "What are the opening hours of the restaurant?" will reflect information of a particular hotel/cruise ship and users will profit from it to understand the answers of members of staff. Not only the language material but the multimedia one (pictures, audio recordings) needs customization (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Access to hotel premises

Concerning the promotional material (offers, notifications etc.), a relational database will be used to facilitate the process of adding or removing information and retrieving the multimedia material of the app; it will be structured in a way that allows adaptation to the needs that may arise. For example, when a new record (text, picture, video) is added in the table, it takes a unique id that can be related to the language and multimedia material of the specific hotel place. The interface of the database will allow hotel personnel to manage (add and delete records) easily.

★ Automatic access to the communicative material

Nowadays, more and more people expect to have access to information in real time through their smartphones. Context aware computing is “a style of computing in which situational and environmental information about people, places and things is used to anticipate immediate needs and proactively offer enriched, situation-aware and usable content, functions and experiences” [6]. There are various technologies offered nowadays, such as GPS technology that is mainly used in the outdoor environment and RFID, NFC and Bluetooth that are mainly used for indoor environments since walls and ceilings constrain the use of GPS [7]. Beacons for example, are very small, simple devices that transmit a radio signal and can be connected with Bluetooth-enabled devices like smartphones. These devices can be placed inside a hotel’s place or in a shop and push notifications on users’ mobile devices with the corresponding dialogue that they may need to use in the specific place.

Moreover, with the use of GPS technology, users who walk around a city can get access to the material they need at the post office, the bank, the shoe store etc. to use the appropriate vocabulary and phrases on any occasion.

Another way to enhance interactivity between users and the app is to use QR Codes. Users can scan a QR Code that they see outside their room or, for example, in the reception area and automatically be redirected to the list of dialogues that are related to the place they find themselves in. With this feature, users can choose from the available dialogues the one that suits them and communicate with people immediately!

4 CONCLUSIONS

Learning to speak a foreign language is not just studying lists of words and expressions. It involves learning vocabulary in context and practicing it in real communicative situations. Interactive mobile apps engage learners (mentally, physically, emotionally) in an active learning process, thus allowing them to practice conversational patterns based on real-life scenarios, to develop their speaking and listening skills and to get a deep feeling of the language they learn.

“Speak on the Spot” meets Green’s [8] all the prerequisites for a successful language learning software. The language content is practical and has the form of authentic everyday conversations that encourage users to communicate in Greek. Audio recording facilitates speaking practice, enables to users pick up on the intonation of Greek and practice their pronunciation alongside that of a native speaker. With the phonetic transcription, users are encouraged to repeat new words and phrases out loud and become more and more confident by recording their voice and improving their pronunciation; the more they practice, the more confident they become. Language material is translated in English or Chinese (with possibility to add other supportive languages) to facilitate the leaning process.

The suggested multifaceted app works offline but it can also work as a real-time assistant with the use of beacons, GPS and similar technologies. Tourists have automatic access to the communicative material when they need it to communicate ‘on the spot’ with the locals in Greek. The app can also be used to promote services of various tourist companies (of hotels, airline companies, malls etc.) and enhance tourist experience through customization of the multimedia content..

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